

NOTES

Mixed Ligand Copper(II) Complexes

S. N. SHETTI*

Department of Chemistry, Birla College, Kalyan-421 304
and

A. S. R. MURTY

Department of Chemistry, Karnatak University,
Dharwad-580 003

*Manuscript received 24 January 1989,
revised 14 November 1990, accepted 28 November 1990*

WE report here the preparation and characterisation of some mixed ligand complexes of copper(II) with isonitrosoacetophenone thiosemicarbazone (INAPT) and N-bases, viz. α -, β - and γ -picolines and morpholine.

Experimental

All chemicals used were of AnalaR grade. The ligand INAPT was prepared as reported elsewhere¹.

Primary Cu^{II} complex: A hot aqueous ethanolic solution of CuCl₂·2H₂O (0.01 mol, 25 ml) was refluxed with hot ethanolic solution of INAPT (0.01 mol, 25 ml). The reddish brown complex separated was filtered, washed successively with water, ethanol and ether and then dried over CaCl₂ under reduced pressure.

Mixed ligand Cu^{II} complexes: To the hot ethanolic solution of the copper-INAPT complex (0.01 mol, 25 ml), ethanolic solution of N-base ligand (0.01 mol) was added and refluxed for 2 h. Dark red coloured complex thus separated was filtered, washed successively with ethanol and ether, and dried over anhydrous CaCl₂ under reduced pressure.

The complexes were analysed for Cu, S and Cl by conventional methods², while C, H and N by microanalytical methods. Conductivity measurements were carried out on an Elico conductivity bridge with a dip-type conductivity cell. Magnetic susceptibility was determined at room temperature by Gouy method. Ir spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 983 spectrophotometer, far-ir spectra (nujol) on a Fourier spectrophotometer, electronic spectra (DMF) on a Cary 2390 spectrophotometer and esr spectra at 298 K on a Varian E-4, X-band spectrometer using cylindrical quartz sample tube operating at 9.32 GHz. DPPH free radical being used as g-marker ($g=2.0023$). Thermograms were recorded on a MOM derivatograph in static air at a heating rate of 10° per min up to 1000°.

Results and Discussion

Elemental analysis and molar conductivity data (Table 1) of the complexes correspond to the stoichio-

metry of [Cu(INAPT-H)Cl] and [Cu(INAPT-H)B]Cl (B=pyridine; α -, β -, γ -picoline; morpholine) for binary and mixed ligand complexes respectively. Non-electrolytic binary complexes ($\lambda_M=15.60 \Omega^{-1} \text{cm}^2 \text{mol}^{-1}$) are converted into 1:1 electrolytes ($\lambda_M=78-90$) on reacting with N-bases indicating the displacement of Cl⁻ ion from coordination sphere by B-ligands.

The room temperature magnetic moment values (1.22–1.61 B.M.) of the complexes are lower than the spin-only value (1.73 B.M.) which further suggests metal-metal interaction in these complexes.

The electronic spectra of the copper complexes displayed bands at 14.2–15.5, 20.8–22.2 and 27.8–29.4 kK which could be assigned to ${}^2B_{2g} \leftarrow {}^2B_{1g}$, ${}^2E_g \leftarrow {}^2B_{1g}$ and intraligand transitions ($\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$ transitions of the azomethine group) respectively, which are characteristic of square-planar geometry³. From the infrared spectral studies of isonitrosoacetophenone thiosemicarbazones, it is obvious that the ligands act as tridentate coordinating through azomethine N, oximino N and thiocarbonyl S donors. This is proved by the following observations. (i) The bands at ~ 3400 (OH) and $\sim 3250 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ (NH) in the ligand became medium or very broad at $3480-3000 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ indicating deprotonation of OH group and non-coordination of terminal NH₂ group. The broadening of the band is also due to inter- and intramolecular hydrogen bonding⁴. (ii) The band at 1615 cm^{-1} (C=N) suffered a positive shift of 5 cm^{-1} furnishing evidence for coordination through N of $-C=N-NH-$ group. (iii) The band at $1001-1010 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ (N-O) shifted to higher frequency by $5-30 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ suggesting the coordination of oxime N⁵. (iv) In the complexes, the bands at ~ 690 (C=S) and at $\sim 770 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ ($\nu_{C=S} + \nu_{C=N}$) underwent hypsochromic as well as hypochromic shifts compared to free ligands, supporting the involvement of S of C=S group in complexation⁶.

The infrared spectra of the mixed ligand complexes suggest the coordination of ring nitrogen of heterocyclic bases ascertained from the positive shift in the ring breathing modes of the complexes compared to the free base. It is suggested that the characteristic aromatic ring breathing vibrations appear in the region $1000-1350 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ in most of the heterocyclic compounds. The $\nu_{C=C}$ and $\nu_{C=N}$ bands of the pyridine ring at ~ 1590 (band I), 1576 (band II), 1480 (band III) and 1445 cm^{-1} (band IV) have undergone various changes on coordination of pyridine ring to copper⁷. This mode of bonding was further confirmed by the presence of ν_{M-N} (pyridine) band at $\sim 285 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ in the complexes⁸. The 320 and 390 cm^{-1} bands of the complexes correspond to ν_{M-S} and ν_{M-N} (NH group) vibrations. The ν_{M-Cl} band at 240 cm^{-1} observed in the primary

TABLE I—ANALYTICAL AND PHYSICAL DATA OF THE COMPLEXES

Compd.	Analysis % Found/(Calcd)				Esr parameters		
	M	S	N	Cl	$g_{\perp}$	$g_{\parallel}$	g_{av}
[Cu(INAPT-H)Cl]	19.74 (19.84)	9.82 (10.01)	16.85 (17.50)	10.91 (11.07)	2.065	2.222	2.117
[Cu(INAPT-H)Py]Cl	15.76 (15.91)	8.10 (8.03)	17.35 (17.54)	8.79 (8.88)	2.070	2.198	2.118
[Cu(INAPT-H) α -Pic]Cl	15.22 (15.37)	7.58 (7.76)	16.97 (16.94)	8.48 (8.58)	2.066	2.241	2.124
[Cu(INAPT-H) β -Pic]Cl	15.28 (15.37)	7.49 (7.76)	16.82 (16.94)	8.42 (8.58)	2.066	2.219	2.117
[Cu(INAPT-H) γ -Pic]Cl	15.38 (15.37)	7.61 (7.76)	16.84 (16.94)	8.51 (8.58)	2.064	2.133	2.087
[Cu(INAPT-H)Mor]Cl	15.54 (15.64)	7.92 (7.89)	17.08 (17.23)	8.56 (8.72)	2.057	2.204	2.106

complex was absent in the far-ir spectra of the mixed ligand complexes, thus confirming the displacement of the Cl^- from coordination sphere as indicated by conductivity data.

B=N of bases

The esr spectra recorded on the powdered samples revealed two g -values ($g_{\parallel}$ and $g_{\perp}$). The trend, $g_{\parallel} > g_{\perp} > g_{DPPH}$ showed that the electron is delocalised in $d_{x^2-y^2}$ orbital of the ground state of Cu^{II} and the spectra are characteristic of axial symmetry. The $G = (g_{\parallel} - 2)/(g_{\perp} - 2)$ values are less than 4, suggesting the exchange interaction between Cu centres in the solid state⁹. The α^2 values (0.45–0.52) indicate appreciable in-plane covalency¹⁰. The spin-orbit coupling constants ($-\lambda_1 = 620-690 \text{ cm}^{-1}$) are less than the free-ion value (-830 cm^{-1}) which further indicates covalent nature of these complexes.

TG study reveals that the complexes suffered loss of heterobases together with Cl^- in the first stage at $\sim 300^\circ$ and then gradual decomposition of the primary ligand upto 500° . Finally, the complexes were decomposed to CuO at $\sim 1000^\circ$.

Acknowledgement

One of the authors (S.N.S.) is thankful to U.G.C., New Delhi, for the award of a Teacher Research Fellowship.

References

1. N. SALDABOIS, A. CIMANIS, S. HILLERS, J. POPELIS, L. N. ALKESREVA, A. ZILJE and A. K. VALYNSKAYA, *Khim. Farm. Zh.*, 1974, **8**, 12.
2. A. I. VOGEL, "A Text Book of Quantitative Inorganic Analysis", 3rd ed., ELBS, London, 1961, pp. 497, 462, 256, 460.
3. B. N. FIGGIS, "Introduction to Ligand Field Theory", Interscience, New York, 1966.
4. C. N. R. RAO, "Chemical Applications of Infrared Spectroscopy", Academic, New York, 1967, pp. 247, 259.
5. A. PALM and M. WERBEN, *Can. J. Chem.*, 1954, **32**, 858; D. M. WILES, B. A. GINGRAS and T. SUPRUNCHUK, *Can. J. Chem.*, 1967, **45**, 469.
6. B. SINGH and K. P. THAKUR, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1974, **36**, 1735.
7. D. A. BALDWIN, A. B. P. LIVER and P. PARISH, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1965, **4**, 150; S. P. SINHA, *Spectrochim. Acta*, 1964, **20**, 899.
8. R. J. H. CLARK and S. C. WILLIAMS, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1965, **4**, 350.
9. B. BOSNICH, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1968, **90**, 627; A. JAGGI, S. CHANDRA and K. K. SHARMA, *Polyhedron*, 1985, **4**, 163.
10. B. J. HATHWAY, *Struct. Bonding (Berlin)*, 1973, **14**, 60; D. KIVELSEN and R. NEIMAN, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1961, **35**, 149.